

On the Study of Polyhalides. Part III.

BY SUSIL KUMAR RAY.

Various attempts have been made to determine the equilibrium relations existing between the polyhalides and their constituents in order to determine their constitution. That a tri-halide, such as that of potassium, barium, etc., may exist in solution is generally accepted. Many of the polyhalides, specially of the heavier alkali metals, have also been separated in the solid state. From measurements of conductivities, viscosities, migration numbers, distribution coefficients and other properties, usually over very limited range of concentrations, various authors have obtained indications of polyhalides to which, on more or less satisfactory grounds, they have been able to assign definite formulæ. References to the literature of the polyhalides of the alkali metals were given in the first part of this work (Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 359). In order to obtain quantitative information of various polyhalides with different cations under the same condition and over a much wider range of concentrations of components than has yet been recorded, the present investigation was undertaken. The formation and dissociation of the chloro-dibromides, chloro-diiodides, bromo-diiodides and polybromides of sodium, potassium, strontium, barium, zinc and cadmium were studied at the temperature of 30° by the method of solubility.

The pure halide of definite concentration was shaken at a temperature of about 35°, with excess of iodine in well stoppered glass bottles for about 12 hours. It was then shaken in a thermostat kept at 30° until equilibrium was attained. Solutions were drawn off into pipettes through cotton wool plugs, any iodine removed by reaction with the cotton being negligible. Iodine was estimated by titration with *N*/100-sodium thiosulphate solution. The solubility of bromine in aqueous solutions of halides of different strengths was determined by shaking up excess of bromine with these solutions, contained in stoppered bottles as in the case of iodine. The bottles were shaken mechanically for 12 hours in a thermostat at 30°. The dissolved bromine in the solution was estimated indirectly, samples being removed by means of a pipette, introduced into excess of concentra-

ted potassium iodide solution and titrated with $N/2$ -sodium thiosulphate solution. Special precautions were taken to prevent any loss of bromine during transference. Any change in the solubility of halogens in presence of different cations was neglected.

From the enhanced solubility of the halogens in the solutions of the chlorides and bromides of sodium, potassium, strontium, barium, zinc and cadmium, there appears to be little doubt that the increased solubility is due to combination of part of the dissolved halogen with the formation of polyhalides of the metals. Attempts to apply the mass action law in systems like these cannot be expected to succeed and there seems no reason to suppose that the formation of any one polyhalide represents the sole action at any particular concentration. However, in the cases of the chloro-dibromides and bromo-diiodides, over a certain range of concentrations, the values of the equilibrium constants calculated on the assumption that tri-halides are formed, are found to be fairly constant. The values of the equilibrium constants in the case of tri-bromo ions were always found to vary, the amount of bromine dissolved in these cases is much greater than that required for the formation of tri-bromo ions, specially in the more concentrated solutions of the bromides. Presumably in these cases higher polybromides, Br_5' , Br_7' , etc., are formed. Moreover, it appears that the tendency of the formation of higher polyhalides is the greatest in the case of polybromides and polyiodides as well. Further it will be seen from the values of the equilibrium constants that in the cases of the chloro-dibromides and chloro-diiodides of the alkali metals, the values remain constant only in dilute solutions, and diminishes greatly with increasing concentrations of the halide. The assumption of the formation of the tri-halides in these cases is only tenable over a very limited range of halide concentration above which higher polyhalides are also formed to a more or less extent. The values in the cases of the polyhalides of the divalent strontium, barium, zinc and cadmium are peculiar in as much as they remain constant only in fairly concentrated solutions, increasing to a very great extent with decreasing halide concentration. The values also show an increase in very concentrated solution as is evident from the Table VI. The cases of the divalent elements are somewhat complicated by the fact that in their cases the dissociation takes place by stages as suggested in Part II of this series (Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 213), as well as to the effect of hydrolysis of the halides on dilution.

The values of the equilibrium constants of the different polyhalides obtained by other investigators as well as by the author by different methods will be found in Part II of this work (*loc. cit.*).

The Formation of ClBr₂ Ions.

TABLE I.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of NaClBr ₂ .		Formation of KClBr ₂ .	
	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .
3	0.8187	1.312	0.9054	1.109
2	0.7435	1.471	0.8287	1.477
1	0.5692	1.544	0.6073	1.621
0.5	0.5057	2.414	0.5287	2.912
0.25	0.4362	3.184	0.4501	3.597
0.125	0.3774	3.188	0.3855	3.795
0.0625	0.3460	3.143	0.3501	3.758
0.0	0.3123	—	0.3123	—

TABLE II.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of Sr ₂ ClBr ₂ .		Formation of Ba ₂ ClBr ₂ .	
	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .
2	0.7491	2.176	0.7703	2.424
1.5	0.6839	2.152	0.6984	2.360
1	0.5886	2.141	0.6203	2.421
0.5	0.4714	2.258	0.4772	2.326
0.25	0.4020	2.215	0.4005	2.258
0.125	0.3615	2.390	0.3803	4.211
0.0625	0.3471	3.084	0.3600	7.532
0.03125	0.3326	4.109	0.3428	12.98
0.0	0.3123	—	0.3123	—

TABLE III.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of $Zn_{\frac{1}{2}} ClBr_2$.		Formation of $Cd_{\frac{1}{2}} ClBr_2$.	
	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .	Solubility of Br in g /10 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .
2	0.6102	1.750	0.4313	2.008
1.5	0.5669	1.786	0.4296	2.043
1	0.5264	1.827	0.4065	2.042
0.5	0.4395	1.848	0.3765	2.039
0.25	0.3861	1.838	0.3537	2.070
0.125	0.3529	1.919	0.3410	2.322
0.0625	0.3340	1.903	0.3301	2.414
0.0	0.3128	—	0.3128	—

The Formation of ClI_2 Ions.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of $NaClI_2$.		Formation of $KClI_2$.	
	Solubility of I in g./25 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .	Solubility of I in g./25 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .
3	0.03263	1.455	0.03443	1.201
2	0.03077	1.542	0.03120	1.492
1	0.02244	1.831	0.02394	2.078
0.5	0.01671	1.824	0.01819	2.094
0.25	0.01352	1.804	0.01436	2.150
0.125	0.01183	1.827	0.01205	2.190
0.0625	0.01094	1.868	0.01173	2.243
0.0	0.00991	—	0.00991	—

TABLE V.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of $\text{Sr}_{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ClI}_2$.		Formation of $\text{Ba}_{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ClI}_2$.	
	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .
2	0.02576	1.768	0.02614	1.886
1.5	0.02318	1.717	0.02389	1.857
1	0.02017	1.780	0.02114	1.908
0.5	0.01609	1.915	0.01678	2.118
0.25	0.01888	2.248	0.01598	2.914
0.125	0.01221	2.458	0.01296	3.272
0.0625	0.01124	2.713	0.01157	3.406
0.0	0.009886	—	0.009886	—

TABLE VI.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of $\text{Zn}_{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ClI}_2$.		Formation of $\text{Cd}_{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ClI}_2$.	
	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant K .
6	0.02943	2.342	0.01811	3.815
4	0.02771	2.130	0.01743	2.841
2	0.02157	1.620	0.01438	1.671
1.5	0.01962	1.506	0.01411	1.652
1	0.01744	1.496	0.01330	1.662
0.5	0.01441	1.515	0.01231	1.714
0.25	0.01288	1.933	0.01207	2.353
0.125	0.01199	2.303	0.01168	3.179
0.0625	0.01119	2.601	0.01091	3.042
0.0	0.009886	—	0.009886	—

The Formation of BrI₂ Ions.

TABLE VII.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of NaBrI ₂ .		Formation of KBrI ₂ .	
	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .
4	0·3257	17·23	0·3608	16·97
3	0·2580	15·37	0·2818	14·94
2	0·1911	14·74	0·1966	13·25
1	0·1076	13·86	0·1053	12·47
0·5	0·06107	13·79	0·05952	12·43
0·25	0·03628	13·76	0·03015	12·49
0·125	0·02457	14·23	0·02375	13·06
0·0625	0·01865	16·54	0·01750	13·96
0·0	0·00991	—	0·00991	—

Solubility of iodine in various concentrations of sodium bromide and potassium bromide at 25° was studied by Bell and Buckley (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 10).

TABLE VIII.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Formation of Sr ₂ BrI ₂ .		Formation of Ba ₂ BrI ₂ .	
	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .	Solubility of I in g./25 c. c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .
2	0·1606	15·57	0·1501	14·62
1·5	0·1393	15·40	0·1270	14·64
1	0·1051	15·60	0·0959	14·72
0·5	0·06299	15·87	0·06004	15·17
0·25	0·03836	15·83	0·03805	15·77
0·125	0·02392	16·50	0·02522	15·99
0·0625	0·01852	16·32	0·01895	16·08
0·0	0·009886	—	0·009886	—

TABLE IX.

Formation of $\text{Cd}_{\frac{1}{2}}\text{BrI}_2$.

Conc. of the halide in normality	Solubility of I in g./25 c.c. sat. solution.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .
2	0.4896	18.16
1	0.4050	17.46
0.5	0.3080	17.49
0.25	0.2368	17.68
0.125	0.1844	17.72
0.0625	0.1501	18.62
0.0	0.0991	

Solubility of Bromine in Bromide Solutions.

From the solubility of bromine in the solutions of the bromides of sodium, potassium, strontium, barium and cadmium, the formation of the tri-bromides of the metals cannot be confirmed; the values of the equilibrium constants are found to vary to a great extent even in very dilute solutions, while in concentrated solutions the amount of bromine dissolved is much greater than that required for the formation of the tri-bromides. In the fairly concentrated solutions, on the other hand, the values of equilibrium constants, calculated on the assumption of the formation of the penta-bromide, are found to give a better result though the values are never constant. It is assumed that in these cases, a mixture of both tri-bromides and penta-bromides and even some higher polybromides are always formed to a more or less extent.

TABLE X.

Solubility of bromine in NaBr and KBr.

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution of	
	NaBr.	KBr.
4	8.127	—
3	4.861	6.013
2	2.458	4.117
1	1.150	2.031
0.5	0.7325	1.144
0.25	0.5137	0.7513
0.125	0.4032	0.5201
0.0625	—	0.4858
0.0	0.3123	0.3123

TABLE XI.

Solubility of bromine in SrBr_2 and BaBr_2 .

Conc. of the halide in normality.	Solubility of Br in g./10 c.c. sat. solution of	
	SrBr_2 .	BaBr_2 .
2	3.024	3.181
1.5	2.596	2.527
1	2.009	2.111
0.5	0.9735	1.034
0.25	0.7003	0.7114
0.125	0.4371	0.4410
0.0625	0.3835	0.3901
0.0	0.3123	0.3123

The solubility of bromine in NaBr of various strengths at 25° was studied by Bell and Buckley (*loc. cit.*). The solubility of bromine in KBr was studied by the following investigators.

Temp.	Authors.	Reference.
0° and 25°	Boericke	<i>Z. Electrochem.</i> , 1905, 11, 57
18.5° and 26.5°	Worley	<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1905, 87, 1107
0°	Jones and Hartmann	<i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1916, 37, 241

TABLE XII.

Solubility of Bromine in CdBr₂.

Conc. of the halide (N)	2	1	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625	0.0
Solubility of Br ₂ g./per 10 c.c. sat. soln.	1.319	1.003	0.8674	0.5845	0.4656	0.4295	0.3123

It will be seen from the preceding tables that the values of the equilibrium constants of any particular polyhalogen ion vary with the nature of the cations as pointed out in Part II of this work (*loc. cit.*). The order of variation as previously found in the cases of sodium and potassium is also found to be the same in the present investigation. The cases of the divalent elements strontium, barium, zinc and cadmium are also found to be analogous to that of the monovalent elements, sodium and potassium. Here also the volume of the cation plays the same part in governing the reaction; zinc having the least of ionic radius exerts the greatest influence and barium with the greatest radius have the least effect. But there appears to exist no relation between the monovalent and the divalent series. The value of the equilibrium constant of NaClBr₂ is greater than the corresponding value of Ba_{1/2}ClBr₂; the ionic volume of barium being greater than that of sodium, the reverse was expected in their cases. This anomaly is to be attributed to the doubly positive charge on the barium ion, the increase of charge being much greater than the increase in radius, the attracting force is much more pronounced in the case of the doubly charged divalent elements.

The constitution of these polyhalides is a matter of much controversy. From the electrical conductivity and the lowering of the freezing point as shown by Schmidt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1895, 9, 431), Sullivan (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 28, 523), Jakovkin (*ibid.*,

1894, 13, 539) and Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1069) it was suggested that the constitution agrees with the assumption that the tri-iodides are the salts of hydrotriiodic acid, HI_3 , with tervalent iodine atoms:

Werner ("Neue Anschauungen auf dem Gebiete der anorganischen Chemie", Leipzig, 1913) regards the tri-halides as addition compounds, so that the tri-halide RCl_3 becomes $\left[\text{Cl} \cdot \text{I} \cdot \text{Cl} \right] \text{R}$, dichloro-iodates on his system of nomenclature. The penta-halides are tetrachloro-iodates analogous to the chloroaurates:

Werner says that the hepta and ennea halides can be explained on the assumption that the co-ordinated positions are occupied by iodine molecules. The non-existence of the tri-chlorides, after Werner "is to be attributed to chlorine being unable to act as a central atom".

According to Ephraim ("Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", Eng. Trans., 1926, p. 260) the constitution of these polyhalides is not very clear. The iodine molecule may be added on to the iodine ion as indicated thus: $\text{I}(\text{I})_2$ or the additional iodine may be more closely attached to the metal thus:

This formula according to him does not indicate an increase in valency of the metal but only a subdivision of its valency. It was also suggested by him that the property of forming polyiodides is connected with the volume of the cation.

None of these formulae explain the general properties of the polyhalides, specially the extreme unstable nature of many of them. The singlet electron linkage as suggested by Cremer and Duncan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 181) explains to a certain extent the instability of

these compounds but the singlet electron linkage theory itself is controversial and in these series of compounds seems to be inadmissible. It is unlikely that the original stable linkage between the atoms of the halogen molecule should be ruptured and a new rather unstable bond should be formed in its place as is required by the assumption of Cremer and Duncan (*loc. cit.*). The author is of the opinion that in these compounds the union is of an electrostatic nature, the charge on the halogen ion causes a displacement of the positive and negative charges in the neutral halogen molecule, so that it becomes polarised; the two being held together by the electrostatic attraction between the negative charge on the halogen ion and the induced opposite charge on the neutral molecule as suggested in Part II of this work (*loc. cit.*). This conception of the electrostatic combination explains the unstability of these compounds satisfactorily while it is the only assumption that can explain the influence of cations on the reactions leading to the formation of the polyhalides (Ray, *loc. cit.*).

SUMMARY₃

By means of solubility, the formation of polyhalides of sodium, potassium, strontium, barium, zinc and cadmium have been confirmed and their dissociation constant at 30° determined and the constitution of the polyhalides has been discussed.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.

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